

Leave **no one behind** Education for **all** Sustainability, Equality and Equity

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Abstract

Dr. Cha-Hsuan Liu is a world-renowned interdisciplinary scholar who is passionate for education, society, and global challenges. Her extensive expertise is shown via her intense participation in scholarly and public engagements. In Dr. Liu's speech, she emphasizes that the rapid processes of globalization, burgeoning technological advancements, and swift environmental and climate changes not only shrink spatial and temporal distances but also alter conventional lifestyles and economic structures. While uneasiness and insecurity towards the rapid changes of our world roams, she believes that crises could serve as catalysts for human and social development through knowledge exchange, mindfulness, and critical thinking. For example, the UN's promotion of Sustainable Development Goals for 2030, the development of Green Technology, and the worldwide publicity campaigns on Social Equality and Social Equity. From an interdisciplinary perspective, Dr. Liu encourages academia, governments, and private sectors work together to fight for societal and ecological challenges faced today and devise responsible strategies. To her, a grand design to address the global issues should over arch education, wellbeing, cultural sustainability. Social policies, business and management, and technological innovation are instruments to accelerate the positive impacts. Her speech elucidates the evolution of humanity from equality, equity, to inclusion. Through collaborative actions, we enhance our common life experiences and inclusive prosperity. She is convinced, by sharing mindfulness and exchanging knowledge and critical insights will further inspire our lives and our living.

Keywords: *education for sustainability, equality and equity, global challenges, interdisciplinary collaboration, sustainable development goals*